

METHODS AND MEANS OF ENSURING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE EDUCATION OF BIOPHYSICS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article, the methods and means of ensuring the effectiveness of the education of biophysics in higher educational institutions are considered.*

Keywords: *higher education, methodological innovations, interactive education, multimedia, traditional teaching.*

Introduction. Currently, the level of development of higher education is one of the criteria indicating the level of its development, which determines the status of a state in the world. The sublime the general level of education, its convenience, improvement and the use of modern technologies in it are among the main indicators that characterize any higher educational and educational system. One of the directions for improving student training in modern universities is the introduction of active and interactive forms of education. In the organization of the process of education in universities, andragogical and continuing education in accordance with the state educational standards of higher and professional education, an individual approach to an individual student based on his personal requirements, taking into account his social and psychological characteristics, is considered a timeless requirement.

Main methodological innovations today related to the use of interactive educational technologies. Interactive technologies help to form professionally important qualities by integrating one of the most important problems of teaching-the Educational, Scientific and professional-practical activities of future specialists. The term "interactive pedagogy" was coined in 1975 by German introduced by researcher Gans Fris. At the same time, interactive education is not fundamentally new in World pedagogy. The concept and technology of interactive education is based on the phenomenon of interaction. (interaction-interaction, interaction)[1].

General secondary and higher education levels there is a discrepancy between. Currently, most applicants cannot take the entrance exams without further preparation. The admission of young people to universities only on the basis of the results of the test is comprehensive in teachers of young people obtaining more information about the level of knowledge is depriving them of such significant opportunities as attracting them to the desired specialty, depending on their ability. To the value of the higher education of modern youth the attitude that is positive in some cases will not.

Students are not interested in learning from the very beginning of their studies at the University. For most of them, it is not knowledge itself that is now important, but only the "document" that you will receive after graduation. Studying at the high school became a kind of education, the problem of "worship" of a diploma. Paid higher education for most young people as the standard of living of the people increases in our country became an easy-to-master finish. Thus, the value of the need for Higher Education has decreased significantly. But there is no decrease in the demand for real specialized knowledge and the value of real science and education.

To solve the problem of Higher Education the system is required to introduce reforms and innovations. With the help of the process of improving pedagogical technologies, it is imperative to update the set of teaching techniques and tools according to the requirements of the time. Currently, innovation activity is one of the most important components of any educational institution, any educational activity. This is a random case not. It is innovational activity that provides the basis for creating competitiveness in higher education.

Research Methodology. A problematic lecture is a question in a lecture, through the problematic character of the task or situation, new knowledge is introduced. At the same time, in cooperation and communication with the teacher, the cognitive process of students is brought closer to research activities. The content of the problem is determined by organizing the search for its solution or combining and analyzing traditional and modern points of view. A problem lecture begins with questions, with the formulation of a problem that must be solved during the presentation of the material.

Lecture-visualization. This type of lecture is the result of a new use of the principle of Orientalism. Lecture by the teacher to prepare this lecture using technical means of teaching educational information on the subject of training or hand-made (diagrams, graphs, drawings, etc.), students are instructed to change the text to a visual form the case consists of rearranging and presenting.

Analysis and results. Lectures in the practice of teaching in higher educational institutions are one of the standard traditional forms of teaching the theoretical foundations of any academic discipline remains. There are a number of cases in the educational process, and the lecture form of teaching cannot be replaced by any of its other forms. Lecture performs the following tasks;

- stimulates (arouses interest in the subject),
- educator, factor (educator provides information)
- develops (evaluates phenomena, develops thinking),
- directs (opens the problem, encourages literature),
- explains (first of all, science is aimed at the formation of basic concepts of science),
- assures (with a focus on the evidence system).
- can make youth and adult listeners meaningful in their free time.

Conclusion

So, the interactive of the lecture the introduction of methods in the modern high school as one of the important directions for improving the training of students and a modern condition for the effective implementation of the competence approach, the following areas were considered:

A double (binary) lecture is a form of problematic lecture in the form of a dialogue between two teachers, or representatives of two scientific directions, or between theoretical and practical directions.

Interactive lecture classes involve passive assimilation of knowledge by students, joint learning, collective, collaborative reading, takes, and both the student and the teacher become subjects of the educational process. This makes it possible to switch professional activities to exemplary and active application in real situations, and, of course, to improve the quality of training of specialists in the future comes.

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